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DIDACTIC POSSIBILITIES OF GAME TECHNOLOGIES IN MASTERING ABSTRACT CONCEPTS IN OPTICS

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Annotation. *The article explores the didactic possibilities of using game technologies in mastering abstract concepts found in the optics section of the high school physics course. It is argued that the theoretical and model nature of optical phenomena complicates students' conceptual understanding. The study was conducted using a quasi-experimental method, comparing the learning outcomes of the experimental and control groups of 8th graders. The experimental group used interactive quizzes, virtual laboratories, simulations, and group game elements. The results of the pre-test and post-test showed that game-based learning increases the quality of education. Statistical analysis confirmed the significant difference between the groups. The survey results revealed an increase in students' learning motivation and cognitive activity. The results of the study show that game technologies are an effective pedagogical tool that reduces conceptual errors in optics and contributes to the systematic acquisition of knowledge.*

Keywords: *optics, game technologies, conceptual errors, conceptual understanding, gamification, physics teaching*

Introduction

In the modern education system, it is more important for students to consciously understand concepts than to mechanically master knowledge. The optics section occupies a special place in the subject of physics, but the abstract nature of the properties of light and optical phenomena poses difficulties for students.

In traditional teaching methods, students often remain as receivers of ready-made information, and their activity is low. This leads to a decrease in students' interest in the subject. To solve these problems, there is a need to introduce innovative pedagogical technologies into the teaching process. As many studies have shown, students often memorize formulas, but do not fully understand the nature of light and the causes and effects of optical phenomena. As a result, they can solve problems, but their ability to apply physical principles in new situations and visualize them remains weak. To reduce this problem, it has been shown that not only formulas, but also conceptual understanding and program-oriented activities are important in teaching [1]. The Spectro-Uno card game developed by Sardinola and colleagues significantly improved students' conceptual understanding of the topic of light [2]. A. Vondmagegn, M. Mengesha, and F. Eshetu in their works consider the difficulties in teaching the topic of geometric optics in physics. The authors emphasize that traditional teaching methods cannot fully form students' conceptual understanding. To address this issue, online platforms, virtual labs, and traditional classroom learning have been integrated into a single system. Research findings have shown that not only do they deepen students' theoretical understanding, but they also increase their interest in the subject [3]. Tolentino and colleagues developed a strategic intervention material based on the game «Light Wars». The study used game-based learning technology to increase students' interest and ensure active participation. The game was designed as a hybrid card and board game format and was developed based on the ADDIE model. Research findings have shown that the game «Light Wars» increased students' conceptual understanding of interference and diffraction [4].

Thus, gamified learning has a number of advantages. First, the introduction of game elements, such as points and badges, into the learning process has been proven to be an effective way to make learning more interesting. Game mechanisms act as learning rewards, offering students visible signs of their achievements and successes. Such an approach increases the motivation not only to better master the learning material, but also to apply the acquired knowledge in real life situations [5]. The second important aspect of gamification is its contribution to the development of team spirit and collective success. It is carried out by encouraging friendly competition, which not only emphasizes individual achievements, but also contributes to the overall progress of the team towards its goals [6]. The third aspect of gamification is its incentive to develop innovative and creative abilities, while the fourth important aspect is to significantly strengthen the process of effective organization of feedback and analysis of the effectiveness of students' learning activities. When students score low points, this serves as a clear signal that they are opening the door to improvement and development. A game-like environment allows for tracking progress and identifying areas that require additional work, which in turn contributes to improving student skills [7].

Materials and methods

The choice of the section «Optics» as an object of study in the physics course has its own methodological significance. Optics, while being one of the fundamental branches of physics, is a section that is very abstract in content, full of complex theoretical concepts, and poses certain difficulties for students to perceive.

Explaining topics such as light propagation, reflection and refraction, lens properties, and the principles of operation of modern optical instruments through innovative game technologies rather than traditional reproducible methods is an effective way to simplify complex material. This approach allows students to experience theoretical knowledge visually and practically, and to retain the material in their long-term memory.

In order to form a system of fundamental knowledge for students in the optics department, it is first necessary to study its structural classification (Figure 1):

1. Geometric optics. This section studies the laws of rectilinear propagation of light in homogeneous transparent media, without taking into account the wave and quantum nature of light. The main attention is paid to the geometric models of light rays, the laws of reflection and refraction, as well as the principles of image formation in optical systems.

2. Wave optics. Here, light is considered as an electromagnetic wave. The section studies fundamental phenomena in which the wave properties of light are clearly observed:

- **Interference** (superposition of waves);
- **Diffraction** (going around obstacles);
- **Polarization** (regulation of the direction of oscillation);
- **Dispersion** (the decomposition of light into a spectrum).

3. Quantum optics. A section that studies the propagation of light and the processes of its interaction with matter (photoelectric effect, luminescence, etc.) from the perspective of a flow of photons (light quanta). At this stage, students develop a modern physical understanding of the duality of light (particle-wave duality).

Systematic teaching of these three structural divisions of optics increases students' cognitive activity and provides the basis for a deep understanding of physical phenomena.

Structural Divisions of Optics

Figure 1. Structural classification of the optics department

Conceptual understanding is the ability of a student to understand physical laws and apply them in different situations. Perkins describes conceptual understanding as the ability to perform various cognitive actions related to a concept, namely, the ability to explain, apply, and transfer knowledge to new situations [8].

The acquisition of scientific concepts occurs at three levels: macroscopic, submicroscopic, and symbolic. The weak connection between these levels limits students' conceptual understanding [9]. This problem is especially evident in the optics section, where students have difficulty relating visually observed phenomena to physical models and formulas of light. In this context, the use of game technologies can connect these levels and allow students to understand optical concepts in a meaningful way.

Figure 2 shows the formation of conceptual understanding through gaming technologies.

Figure 2. Formation of a conceptual understanding

Many studies have shown that the introduction of game technologies into the learning process increases students' conceptual understanding, motivation for learning, and activity [10]. The study was conducted using a quasi-experimental method. Two parallel classes of 8th grade students participated in the experiment. In the experimental group, the section of physics «Optics» was taught using game technologies, while in the control group, traditional teaching methods were used. The following methods were used in the study:

- preliminary test (pre-test);
- final test (post-test);
- survey;
- control;
- statistical analysis.

Game elements used in the experimental group: interactive quizzes; virtual laboratories; simulations (PhET); group competitions; role-playing games.

In the lesson structure, game elements were introduced at the following stages:

1. **The period of curiosity** – Draw students' attention to the lesson through the game «Who is faster?»;

2. **The period of learning a new lesson** – performing practical tasks through simulations;

3. **Approval period** – solving problems in a game format;

4. **Conclusion period** – Systematize knowledge through the game «Saykestender»;

5. **Reflection period** – students' self-assessment.

The control group used traditional methods: teacher explanations, working with a textbook, and problem solving.

Results and discussions

The results of the study showed that there were significant positive changes in the experimental group. According to the pre-test results, the initial level of both groups was similar. However, in the post-test results, the average score of the experimental group increased significantly, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Pre-test / post-test results (15 points)

Group	Pre-test	Post-test	Difference
Experimental	7.8	13.4	5.6
Control	8.1	9.6	1.5

The results of statistical analysis (Mann–Whitney test) showed that the difference between the experimental and control groups was statistically significant. According to the table, the critical value of the U-criterion was equal to 64. Since the obtained empirical value is less than this critical value, the null hypothesis (H0) is rejected. Therefore, the alternative hypothesis (H1) is accepted. In other words, we conclude that the use of gaming technologies has a more positive effect on the quality of students' education than traditional teaching methods.

The survey results also showed that students rated learning through games positively. Students noted that the lessons were interesting, that the games helped them understand, and that they were more engaged (Table 2).

Table 2. Survey results (average score)

Indicator	Average score (out of 5)
The lesson was interesting.	4.6
Games helped to understand	4.7
I understood the topic well.	4.5
I was active.	4.4

Conclusion

The effect of using game technologies in teaching the optics section of physics on students' conceptual understanding, learning motivation, and cognitive activity was experimentally studied. The effectiveness of game-based learning was proven by analyzing the results of the pre-test, final test, and questionnaire. The results of the study showed that lessons based on game technologies in the experimental group contributed to significantly higher results in comparison with the initial level of knowledge of students. When comparing the results of the pre-test and post-test, it was found that the level of knowledge of students in the experimental group on the propagation of light, reflection, refraction, and properties of lenses significantly increased. In the control group, no such significant increase was observed. Statistical analysis (Mann-Whitney U-test and Z-statistic) also confirmed that this difference was statistically significant ($p = 0.007 < 0.05$). This proves that gaming technologies can be an effective tool in the learning process.

In conclusion, game technologies are an important didactic tool in mastering abstract concepts in the optics department. Therefore, the systematic use of game technologies in teaching physics is an effective way to improve the quality of education.

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